

Investigation of copper complex solution with new ligand *o*-chlorobenzenediazoaminobenzene-*p*-azobenzene and determination of trace copper in wastewater

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The synthesis of *o*-chlorobenzenediazoaminobenzene-*p*-azobenzene (*o*-CDA-*p*-AB) has been carried out. In basic medium, copper forms a sensitive complex Cu(*o*-CDA-*p*-AB)₂. Its cumulative stability constant K_c is 3.19×10^{10} and its real molar absorptivity $\epsilon = 8.96 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 500 nm. Beer's law is obeyed for 0.15–5.0 μg of copper in 25 ml of solution. The method has been applied satisfactorily for the determination of copper in wastewater.

Azo dyes are the usual reagents for copper(II)¹, but they are not highly sensitive for the determination of trace amounts of copper. In the present study, *o*-chlorobenzenediazoaminobenzene-*p*-azobenzene (*o*-CDA-*p*-AB) has been employed.

The compound was found soluble in acetone, ethanol and aqueous alkali but insoluble in water. It is yellow in weakly acidic, neutral and weakly alkaline media but violet in strongly alkaline medium. The ligand reacts with copper in strongly alkaline medium to form a stable complex having the maximum absorption at 500 nm. The complex characteristics of copper-*o*-CDA-*p*-AB complex has also been determined containing the complexation ratio, the true molar absorptivity, the stepwise stability constant and cumulative one. The method has been applied for the determination of copper in wastewater.

Principle :

From the following expression is developed for the determination of the real absorbance (A_c) of metal (M) complex (ML_γ) produced with a ligand (L).

$$A_c = \frac{\Delta A - \beta \Delta A'}{1 - \alpha \beta}$$

The terms, ΔA and $\Delta A'$ are the absorbances of the mixed solution of ML_γ and excess L measured at wavelengths λ_2 and λ_1 against the reagent blank, respectively. The coefficients, α and β are the correction factors and computed as

$$\alpha = \frac{\epsilon_{ML_\gamma}^{\lambda_1}}{\epsilon_{ML_\gamma}^{\lambda_2}} \quad \text{and} \quad \beta = \frac{\epsilon_L^{\lambda_2}}{\epsilon_L^{\lambda_1}}$$

The terms $\epsilon_{ML_\gamma}^{\lambda_1}$, $\epsilon_{ML_\gamma}^{\lambda_2}$, $\epsilon_L^{\lambda_1}$ and $\epsilon_L^{\lambda_2}$ are the molar absorptivities of ML_γ and L at wavelengths λ_1 and λ_2 , respectively.

The amount ratio (γ) of L to complex M in their reaction may be expressed as follows

$$\gamma' = \eta \times \frac{C_L}{C_M}$$

$$\text{where } \eta = \frac{\alpha \Delta A - \Delta A'}{(1 - \alpha \beta) A'_0}$$

The term, η indicates the reacted percentage of L and δ the cell thickness (cm). The terms, C_M and C_L are the concentrations (mol dm^{-3}) of M and L in the beginning. A'_0 is the absorbance of the blank measured at wavelength λ_1 . If γ' reaches maximum and remains constant, it is thought that $\gamma = \gamma'$, where γ is a natural number, termed the composition ratio of the complex produced.

All of above equations have been reported earlier². The following equation is the first to be developed for the determination of the stepwise stability constant and the cumulative one of a complex. From Fig. 1 and the following reaction,

the following equations are obtained,

$$K_n = \frac{C_{ML_n}}{[C_{L_n-(n-1)} C_M - C_M L_n](C_M - C_{ML_n})} \\ (C_M - C_{ML_n}) \delta \epsilon_{ML_{n-1}}^{\lambda_2} + C_{ML_n} \delta \epsilon_{ML_n}^{\lambda_2} = A_{cn}$$

where C_{L_n} indicates L concentration (mol dm^{-3}) at any point between $C_{L(n-1)}$ and C_{L_n} . Therefore, the following K_n expression is established,

$$K_n = \frac{\delta\Delta\epsilon_n (A_{cn} - \delta C_M \epsilon_{n-1})}{(A_{cn} - \delta C_M \epsilon_{n-1} - \delta\Delta\epsilon_n C_M) [A_{cn} - \delta C_M \epsilon_{n-1} + \delta\Delta\epsilon_n (nC_M - C_M - C_{L_n})]}$$

where ϵ_{n-1} indicates the absorptivity of ML_{n-1} at wavelength λ_2 and $\Delta\epsilon_n = \epsilon_{ML_n}^{\lambda_2} - \epsilon_{ML_{n(n-1)}}^{\lambda_2}$. Here, $\epsilon_0 = 0$, when $n = 1$. Further, the cumulative stability constant (K_c) of ML_γ is expressed as

$$K_c = \prod_{n=1}^{\gamma} K_n$$

The above principle is named spectral correction theory and its method as β -correction spectrophotometry. It is one of the dual-wavelength analytical methods, but different from the others³ in principle and operation.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectra: The absorption spectra of *o*-CDA-*p*-AB and Cu-*o*-CDA-*p*-AB (Fig. 2) showed λ_{max} at 410 and 500 nm, respectively. From curves 1 and 2, α and β are calculated to be 0.27 and 0.065, respectively. The real absorbance of Cu-*o*-CDA-*p*-AB at 500 nm is expressed as $A_c = 1.02 (\Delta A - 0.065\Delta A')$. Here, A_c value is more than the measured ΔA at 500 nm because $\Delta A'$ at 410 nm is less than zero. Therefore, the β -correction method has high sensitivity than the ordinary spectrophotometry.

Fig. 1. Effect of ligand (L) concentration on real absorbance (A_c) and complexation ratio (γ'): (1) γ' , (2) A_c .

Effect of *o*-CDA-*p*-AB concentration: The results of procedure B, by varying the addition of $0.200 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3}$ *o*-CDA-*p*-AB, are shown in Fig. 3. From curves 1-3, both A_c and γ' of each solution may be calculated and their curves are shown in Fig. 4. The A_c value approached maximum (curve 2) when *o*-CDA-*p*-AB concentration was

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra of *o*-CDA-*p*-AB and its Cu^{II} complex solution at pH 12 and in presence of Tween 80: (1) $0.040 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3}$ *o*-CDA-*p*-AB against water reference, (2) $\text{Cu}(\text{o-CDA-p-AB})_2$ solution against water, (3) 0.20 mg dm^{-3} Cu^{II} complexed solution with $0.040 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3}$ *o*-CDA-*p*-AB against a reagent blank

more than $0.024 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3}$. In this work, 5.0 ml of $0.200 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3}$ *o*-CDA-*p*-AB was added. Also, γ' reached constant (curve 1) when *o*-CDA-*p*-AB concentration was over $0.024 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3}$. The formed complex should be expressed as $\text{Cu}(\text{o-CDA-p-AB})_2$. From Fig. 4, K_1 , K_2 , K_c and ϵ values of complex $\text{Cu}(\text{o-CDA-p-AB})_2$ were calculated in the recommended conditions (room temperature 20° and ionic strength 0.01 M). The results were as follows: $\epsilon = 1.90 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $K_1 = 6.02 \times 10^5$, $\epsilon = 8.96 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $K_2 = 5.28 \times 10^4$ and $K_c = 3.19 \times 10^{10}$. The K_c value was similar to that obtained by the continuous variation and equilibrium methods⁴. We found that $\epsilon_{\text{Cu}(\text{o-CDA-p-AB})} > \epsilon_{\text{Cu}(\text{o-CDA-p-AB})_2}$ and $K_{\text{Cu}(\text{o-CDA-p-AB})_2} > K_{\text{Cu}(\text{o-CDA-p-AB})}$.

Fig. 3. Effect of *o*-CDA-*p*-AB concentration at pH 12 and in presence of Tween 80: (1) reagent blank at 410 nm against water, (2) Cu-*o*-CDA-*p*-AB complexed solution containing $5.0 \mu\text{g}$ of Cu at 500 nm against reagent blank, (3) same as (2) but at 410 nm

Effects of pH and addition of Tween 80: By varying pH of Cu-*o*-CDA-*p*-AB solution, we found that its absorption at 500 nm approached maximum between pH 11.5 and 12.5, hence in this work pH 12 was selected. The nonionic surfactant Tween 80 was helpful to increase the analytical sensitivity. The absorption remained constant between 1 and 5 ml addition of 2% Tween 80. Hence, 2 ml of Tween 80 solution was used and the absorbance was found about 2 times higher than that in its absence. The formation of Cu-*o*-CDA-*p*-AB complex was complete within 5 min and the absorbance remained constant for 10 h.

Calibration graph : A calibration graph was constructed by adding varying amounts of copper, then operating and measuring each according to procedure A. The calibration graph was linear in the range 0–5.0 $\mu\text{g Cu}$. The equation was $A_c = 0.068C_{\text{Cu}} - 0.002$, where C_{Cu} is the amount of copper (μg). The linear correlation coefficient was 0.9995. The detection of copper was 0.006 mg dm^{-3} for an absorbance of 0.010. Ten replicated determinations of standard solution containing 0.5 $\mu\text{g Cu}^{\text{II}}$ revealed relative standard deviation of 2.7%.

Effect of foreign ions : Once procedure C was carried out, for 2.00 $\text{mg dm}^{-3} \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$, none of the following ions affected the determination (error <10%) : 1000 $\text{mg dm}^{-3} \text{K}^+$, Na^+ , NH_4^+ , SO_4^{2-} , F^- , Cl^- , NO_3^- ; 200 $\text{mg dm}^{-3} \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$, Mg^{II} , Fe^{II} , Al^{III} , Ti^{IV} , Be^{II} ; 50 $\text{mg dm}^{-3} \text{Mn}^{\text{II}}$, Co^{II} , Zn^{II} , Ni^{II} , Ce^{IV} , Sn^{II} , Fe^{III} , Ga^{III} , V^{V} , Cr^{III} ; 10 $\text{mg dm}^{-3} \text{Cd}^{\text{II}}$, Hg^{II} , Ag^{I} , Au^{III} .

Fig. 4. Effect of *o*-CDA-*p*-AB concentration on A_c and γ' . (1) complexation ratio, γ' , (2) real absorbance, A_c .

Analysis of wastewater samples : Using the above procedures, copper in three samples was determined. The relative standard deviation (mean of six determinations) was less than 3.3% and the recovery of copper between 92.0 and 104%. Therefore, the precision and accuracy of the method recommends the determination of trace amounts of copper in wastewater.

Experimental

o-CDA-*p*-AB was prepared by diazotizing *o*-chlorophenylamine with sodium nitrite at 0°, then coupling *p*-aminobenzene in LiOH solution at 0°. The solution was adjusted to pH 7–8 with LiOH solution kept for 12 h at room temperature. The resulting red solid product was dried under reduced pressure.

A TU-1201 spectrophotometer with 1.0 cm cells was used. *o*-CDA-*p*-AB solution (0.20 mmol dm^{-3}) was prepared in ethanol (Bengbu Chemical). Standard copper solution (1.00 mg dm^{-3}) was prepared. The buffer solution was prepared by dissolving sodium tetraboratetraborate (Yongqing Chemical; 50 g) in distilled water (400 ml) and adjusted to pH 12 with 10% NaOH. A 2% Tween 80

(Shanghai reagents) solution was used for increasing the analytical sensitivity and solubility of the ligand and its Cu complex. A 1% solution of dimethyl phthalate (DMP, Shanghai Chemical) was prepared in HCl and used to complex most of the heavy metal ions involving Cu^{II} . The formed complexes may be extracted into chloroform (Huainan Chemical) layer by DMP. A 1% H_2O_2 (Shanghai Chemical) solution was prepared and used to dissociate Cu-DMP complex to Cu^{II} ion in aqueous layer. All reagents were of A.R. grade.

Determination of copper(II). Procedure A : A mixture of an aliquot of copper (not more than 5 μg) and solutions of buffer (5 ml), Tween 80 (2 ml) and *o*-CDA-*p*-AB (0.5 ml) was diluted to 25 ml with water and after 5 min its absorbance was measured at 410 and 500 nm against a blank reagent. Combining with the measured data A_c , α and β were calculated.

Determination of Cu-*o*-CDA-*p*-AB complex characteristic factors. Procedure B : A series of 0.20 mmol dm^{-3} *o*-CDA-*p*-AB solutions of varying amount were prepared (0.50 to 5.00 ml). To each solution copper solution (5 $\mu\text{g Cu}$), buffer solution (5 ml) and Tween 80 solution (2 ml) were added and diluted to 25 ml with water. After 5 min, absorbances were measured at 410 and 500 nm, respectively, against a blank reagent. The characteristic factors were calculated from the data.

Extraction of trace copper in wastewater. Procedure C : A known volume of a wastewater (containing less than 5.0 $\mu\text{g Cu}$) was diluted with distilled water (~80 ml) and adjusted to pH 5–6 with 1 mol dm^{-3} NaOH. Then 6 mol dm^{-3} HCl (2 ml), EDTA solution (1 ml) and DMP solution (5 ml) were added and diluted to 100 ml with distilled water. Cu was extracted from this solution with chloroform (2 \times 10 ml). A 1% H_2O_2 solution was used for stripping copper in the organic layer. The absorbances of the aqueous layer were measured according to procedure A.

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